

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF COMPLEX
FERRO AND FERRICYANIDES. PART III. CONDUCTOMETRIC
STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF COPPER
FERROCYANIDE

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The composition of copper ferrocyanide has been studied by the conductometric titration of copper sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide and the results discussed in relation to the conclusions derived from thermometric and potentiometric titrations (Parts I and II).

In previous parts of this series (*this Journal*, 1947, 24, 487, 499) the composition of copper ferrocyanide has been studied by thermometric and potentiometric methods of titrations. In this paper the composition has been studied by the conductometric titrations of copper sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide. The conductometric results have been discussed *vis a vis* the conclusions derived from thermometric and potentiometric titrations.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

'Analar' (B.D.H.) reagents were used. Preparation of standard solutions and all further dilutions were made with conductivity water. The conductivities were measured by Kohlrausch's Universal Bridge (W. G. Pye Ltd.) As a source of alternating current a small induction coil was used, the point of balance being indicated by the minima of sound in the telephone. The cell used was of Arrhenius type and was immersed in a thermostat whose temperature was controlled within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. For carrying the titrations 10 c.c. of one of the reagents were taken in the conductivity cell, while the other was added from the burette. The conductance of the solution after each addition was measured. This was carried on till about 1 to 2 c.c. of the titrating liquid was added in excess of the equivalence point, which could be easily known from the increase or decrease in the conductivities observed. The conductance obtained after each addition was corrected for dilution by multiplying the observed conductance by $V/10$, where 'V' is the total volume of the solution, and 10 c.c. refer to the volume of the reactant originally taken in the cell (Davies, "The Conductivity of Solutions", p. 238). Curves were plotted between the corrected conductance so obtained against the volume of the titrant. The equivalence point was obtained as a point of intersection of the two portions of the curve. In the case where the two portions were joined by a curve of inflection, the middle point of inflection was taken as the equivalence point.

Using different concentrations of the two salt solutions, titrations were followed by the direct and reverse methods of titrations (*i.e.*, when copper sulphate from burette was added to potassium ferrocyanide taken in the cell and *vice versa*). Titrations were also done in the presence of alcohol up to a total concentration of 20% by volume. $M/5$ solution of copper sulphate would be referred as A/1 solution and $M/4.94$ solution of potassium ferrocyanide solution, as A/1 solution of K_4FeCy_6 .

Direct Conductometric Titrations

Copper sulphate from the burette was added to potassium ferrocyanide in the cell, and mixed with varying amounts of alcohol.

TABLE I

Vol. of A/10-K₄FeCy₆ = 10 c.c. Alcohol = nil. (Fig. 1, curve 1).

A/1-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/1-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/1-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	23.26 × 10 ⁻³	0.8 c.c.	10.8 c.c.	20.50 × 10 ⁻³	1.3 c.c.	11.3 c.c.	19.41 × 10 ⁻³
0.2	10.2	22.66	1.0	11.0	19.82	1.4	11.4	19.83
0.4	10.4	21.89	1.1	11.1	19.38	1.5	11.5	20.84
0.6	10.6	21.20	1.2	11.2	19.31	1.6	11.6	21.81
						1.7	11.7	22.63

TABLE II

A/10-K₄FeCy₆ soln. = 9 c.c. Alcohol = 1 c.c. (Fig. 2, curve 2).

A/1-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho.)	A/1 CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho.)
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	15.04 × 10 ⁻³	1.1 c.c.	11.1 c.c.	13.62 × 10 ⁻³
0.4	10.4	14.82	1.2	11.2	13.75
0.6	10.6	14.42	1.3	11.3	14.31
0.8	10.8	14.04	1.4	11.4	15.20
1.0	11.0	13.72	1.7	11.7	16.84

TABLE III

A/10-K₄FeCy₆ soln. = 8 c.c. Alcohol = 2 c.c. (Fig. 2, curve 3).

A/1-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/1-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/1-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	95.24 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.6 c.c.	10.6 c.c.	94.2 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.1 c.c.	11.1 c.c.	96.11 × 10 ⁻⁴
0.2	10.2	96.68	0.7	10.7	93.45	1.2	11.2	101.4
0.4	10.4	95.82	0.9	10.9	92.76	1.5	11.5	115.6
0.5	10.5	95.06	1.0	11.0	92.81	1.6	11.6	119.0

TABLE IV

Vol. of A/10-K₄FeCy₆ = 10 c.c. Alcohol = nil. (Fig. 3, curve 4).

A/2-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/2-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/2-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	23.53 × 10 ⁻³	1.6 c.c.	11.6 c.c.	21.40 × 10 ⁻³	2.8 c.c.	12.8 c.c.	21.16 × 10 ⁻³
0.4	10.4	23.01	2.2	12.2	20.62	3.0	13.0	21.85
0.8	10.8	22.50	2.4	12.4	20.34	3.2	13.2	22.56
1.2	11.2	21.93	2.6	12.6	20.39	3.4	13.4	23.32

TABLE V

Vol. of A/10-K₄FeCy₆ = 9 c.c. Alcohol = 1 c.c. (Fig. 4, curve 5).

A/2-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/2-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/2-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	15.15 × 10 ⁻³	1.8 c.c.	11.8 c.c.	14.48 × 10 ⁻³	2.6 c.c.	12.6 c.c.	15.81 × 10 ⁻³
0.4	10.4	15.18	2.0	12.0	14.28	2.8	12.8	16.00
0.8	10.8	15.07	2.2	12.2	14.27	3.0	13.0	16.90
1.2	11.2	14.84	2.4	12.4	14.51	3.2	13.2	17.49

TABLE VI

Vol. of A/10-K₄FeCy₆ = 8 c.c. Alcohol = 2 c.c. (Fig. 4, curve 6).

A/2-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/2-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/2-CuSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)
0.4 c.c.	10.4 c.c.	10.15 × 10 ⁻³	1.8 c.c.	11.8 c.c.	10.00 × 10 ⁻³	2.4 c.c.	12.4 c.c.	11.07 × 10 ⁻³
0.8	10.8	10.09	2.0	12.0	10.08	2.6	12.6	11.89
1.2	11.2	10.05	2.2	12.2	10.25	2.8	12.8	12.59
1.6	11.6	10.00	2.2	12.2	10.47	3.0	13.0	12.94

Reverse Conductometric Titrations

K₄Fe(CN)₆ solution from the burette was added to CuSO₄ solution in the cell and mixed with varying amounts of alcohol.

TABLE VII

Vol. of A/10-CuSO₄ = 1.1 c.c. Alcohol = nil. (Fig. 5, curve 7).

A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	8.33 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.8 c.c.	10.8 c.c.	12.83 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.3 c.c.	11.3 c.c.	15.44 × 10 ⁻⁴
0.2	10.2	9.31	1.0	11.0	14.10	1.4	11.4	16.01
0.4	10.4	10.50	1.1	11.1	14.80	1.6	11.6	17.80
0.6	10.6	11.72	1.2	11.2	15.12	1.8	11.8	19.77

TABLE VIII

Vol. of A/10-CuSO₄ = 9 c.c. Alcohol = 1 c.c. (Fig. 5, curve 8).

A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	62.11 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.8 c.c.	10.8 c.c.	100.9 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.3 c.c.	11.3 c.c.	118.7 × 10 ⁻⁴
0.2	10.2	68.00	1.0	11.0	109.5	1.4	11.4	125.3
0.4	10.4	78.52	1.1	11.1	111.0	1.6	11.6	139.0
0.6	10.6	89.07	1.2	11.2	114.0	1.8	11.8	155.3

TABLE IX

Vol. of A/10-CuSO₄ = 8 c.c. Alcohol = 2 c.c. (Fig. 5, curve 9).

A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	31.75 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.6 c.c.	10.6 c.c.	59.35 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.2 c.c.	11.2 c.c.	84.22 × 10 ⁻⁴
0.2	10.2	40.00	0.8	10.8	70.59	1.4	11.4	97.01
0.4	10.4	49.06	1.0	11.0	76.67	1.6	11.6	111.0
			1.1	11.1	79.55	1.7	11.7	117.0

TABLE X

Vol. of A/10-CuSO₄ = 10 c.c. Alcohol = nil. (Fig. 6, curve 10).

A/4 K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	78.13 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.0 c.c.	12.0 c.c.	141.7 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.7 c.c.	12.7 c.c.	158.4 × 10 ⁻⁴
0.4	10.4	88.50	2.2	12.2	147.9	2.8	12.8	162.7
0.8	10.8	100.9	2.4	12.4	150.3	2.9	12.9	168.6
1.2	11.2	113.7	2.6	12.6	154.6	3.2	13.2	183.5
1.6	11.6	126.4				3.6	13.6	206.0

TABLE XI

Vol. of A/10-CuSO₄ = 9 c.c. Alcohol = 1 c.c. (Fig. 6, curve 11).

A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	49.50 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.0 c.c.	12.0 c.c.	110.1 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.4 c.c.	12.4 c.c.	117.0 × 10 ⁻⁴
0.4	10.4	60.11	2.1	12.1	111.0	2.6	12.6	124.2
0.8	10.8	71.53	2.2	12.2	112.4	2.8	12.8	133.1
1.2	11.2	83.55	2.3	12.3	114.4	3.2	13.2	152.6
1.6	11.6	97.90				3.4	13.4	160.5

TABLE XII

Vol. of A/10-CuSO₄ = 8 c.c. Alcohol = 2 c.c. (Fig. 6, curve 12).

A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Cor. condy. (mho)
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	31.75 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.6 c.c.	11.6 c.c.	74.82 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.4 c.c.	12.4 c.c.	92.54 × 10 ⁻⁴
0.4	10.4	40.79	1.8	11.8	79.77	2.8	12.8	107.5
0.8	10.8	50.94	2.0	12.0	82.46	3.2	13.2	122.8
1.2	11.2	62.57	2.1	12.1	84.02	3.4	13.4	131.3
			2.2	12.2	85.90			

The variations in the titre values in presence of alcohol support the hydrolytic behaviour of copper ferrocyanide.

DISCUSSION

Considering the strengths of the solutions of copper sulphate (M/4.8) and potassium ferrocyanide (M/5.0), the theoretical titre values for 10 c.c. of K₄FeCy₆ for the formation of the compounds K₂CuFeCy₆, Cu₂FeCy₆ and K₂Cu₃(FeCy₆)₂ in direct titration would be 9.6, 19.2 and 14.4 c.c. respectively of copper sulphate solution. Theoretical titre values for the formation of the above compounds in the reverse titrations would be 10.42, 5.21 and 6.95 respectively of ferrocyanide solution.

In view of the hydrolysable character of the compound, the titre values in the aqueous medium in the case of direct titrations should be higher than the theoretical one. Compound K₂CuFeCy₆ would require 9.6 c.c. of CuSO₄ for 10 c.c. of K₄FeCy₆. But in the case of direct titrations the compound K₂Cu₃(FeCy₆)₂ is also likely to be formed, as has actually been observed in the thermometric and potentiometric studies. The observed titre values 12.8 to 13.54 in aqueous medium in the direct titrations therefore suggest that a mixture of K₂CuFeCy₆ and K₂Cu₃(FeCy₆)₂ is formed, and the average molecular proportion on the basis of conductometric results, comes to 1 : 3. The

FIG. 1

FIG. 3

FIG. 2

FIG. 4

decrease in the titre value in the presence of alcohol is explained as being due to the suppression of hydrolysis of the mixed compound formed.

FIG. 5

FIG. 6

In the reverse titrations the observed titre value 6.6 to 6.7 c.c. in aqueous medium is slightly lower than the theoretical one (6.9 c.c.) required for the formation of $K_2Cu_3(FeCy_6)_2$. In the presence of alcohol there is a gradual increase of the observed titre values which very nearly approach the theoretical one. These results again support the hydrolytic behaviour of copper ferrocyanide and the formation of $K_2Cu_3(FeCy_6)_2$ when the compound is precipitated in excess of $CuSO_4$.

Along with hydrolysis, adsorption of Cu^{++} and $Fe(CN)^{4-}$ ions also affects the composition of copper ferrocyanide, but the role of adsorption may be apparently suppressed and may not be accounted for by the titre values in consequence of the hydrolytic behaviour of such compounds. Quantitative estimations of the adsorption of Cu^{++} and $Fe(CN)^{4-}$ ions are in progress.

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